

Impact Factor: 6.145

ISSN: 2181-0990
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0990
www.tadqiqot.uz

JRHUNR

JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH

TADQIQOT.UZ

VOLUME 6,
ISSUE 1 **2025**

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Журнал репродуктивного здоровья и уро-
нефрологических исследований

JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH

Главный редактор: Б.Б. НЕГМАДЖАНОВ

Учредитель:

Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет

Tadqiqot.uz

Ежеквартальный
научно-практический
журнал

№ 1
2025

ISSN: 2181-0990

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0990

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ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ВЫБОР МЕТОДА УШИВАНИЯ МАТКИ ПРИ КЕСАРЕВОМ СЕЧЕНИИ: АНАЛИЗ АНАМНЕСТИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ.....	76
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UDC 618.5-089.888.61

JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH

ЖУРНАЛ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ И УРО-НЕФРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ISSN: 2181-0990
www.tadqiqot.uz

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IMPACT OF UTERINE CLOSURE METHOD AFTER CESAREAN SECTION ON REPRODUCTIVE OUTCOMES

For citation: Valiev Shukhrat, Impact of uterine closure method after cesarean section on reproductive outcomes journal of reproductive health and uro-nephrology research 2025 vol 6 issue 1, pp.72-75

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15110881>

ABSTRACT

A study was conducted on 496 women aged 18 to 42 years who underwent a cesarean section. Based on the uterine closure method, all patients were divided into two groups: Group 1 – 240 (48%) women who underwent modified uterine closure, and Group 2 – 256 (52%) women with traditional closure. The study revealed that the method of uterine closure affects the frequency of reproductive losses, the duration of the intergenetic interval, and the incidence of gynecological diseases. In the modified closure group, there was a decrease in the frequency of spontaneous miscarriages, non-developing pregnancies, and inflammatory processes. The results confirm the need for optimizing uterine closure techniques to improve reproductive outcomes and the integrity of the uterine scar.

Keywords: uterine closure; cesarean section; reproductive losses; gynecological diseases; contraception.

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KESAR KESISH AMALIYOTIDAN SO'NG BACHADON YOPISSH USULINING REPRODUKTIV NATIJALARGA TA'SIRI

ANNOTASIYA

18 yoshdan 42 yoshgacha bo'lgan 496 nafar ayol ustida o'rganish o'tkazildi. Bachadon tikish usuliga qarab barcha bemorlar ikki guruhga bo'lindi: 1-guruh – 240 (48%) ayolga modifikatsiyalangan bachadon tikish usuli qo'llanilgan, 2-guruh – 256 (52%) ayolga esa an'anaviy tikish usuli qo'llanilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari bachadon tikish usuli reproduktiv yo'qotishlar chastotasi, intergenetik interval davomiyligi va ginekologik kasalliklar tez-tez uchrashiga ta'sir qilishi mumkinligini ko'rsatdi. Modifikatsiyalangan tikish usuli qo'llanilgan guruhda spontan abortlar, rivojlanmaydigan homiladorliklar va yallig'lanish jarayonlari kamroq kuzatildi. Natijalar bachadon tikish texnikasini optimallashtirish reproduktiv natijalarni va bachadon chandiq mustahkamligini yaxshilash zaruriyatini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: bachadon yopish; kesar kesish; reproduktiv yo'qotishlar; ginekologik kasalliklar; kontratsepsiya.

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ВЛИЯНИЕ МЕТОДА УШИВАНИЯ МАТКИ ПОСЛЕ КЕСАРЕВА СЕЧЕНИЯ НА РЕПРОДУКТИВНЫЕ ИСХОДЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Проведено обследование 496 женщин, перенесших кесарево сечение, в возрасте от 18 до 42 лет. С учетом метода ушивания матки все пациентки были разделены на 2 группы: 1 группа – 240 (48%) женщин, у которых применялось модифицированное ушивание матки, и 2 группа – 256 (52%) женщин с традиционным ушиванием. Проведённые исследования показали, что метод ушивания матки влияет на частоту репродуктивных потерь, длительность интергенетического интервала и частоту гинекологических заболеваний. В группе модифицированного ушивания выявлено снижение частоты самопроизвольных выкидышей, неразвивающейся беременности и воспалительных процессов. Результаты подтверждают необходимость оптимизации техники ушивания матки для улучшения репродуктивных исходов и состояния рубца на матке.

Ключевые слова: ушивание матки; кесарево сечение; репродуктивные потери; гинекологические заболевания; контрацепция.

The global rate of cesarean sections (CS) continues to rise, resulting in a growing number of women with uterine scars and associated long-term complications. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in some countries, the proportion of CS can reach 30–50% of all deliveries, highlighting the importance of ensuring high-quality healing of the postoperative scar [1]. The main complications following CS include scar dehiscence, niche formation, thinning of the residual myometrium, menstrual disorders, infertility, and uterine rupture in subsequent pregnancies [2,3]. Despite active research in this area, there remains no single optimal standard for uterine closure that would minimize the risk of scar-related defects and improve long-term gynecological and obstetric outcomes [4].

The quality of uterine scar healing largely depends on the suturing technique used. Currently, a range of methods is employed: single- or double-layer closure, locked or unlocked sutures, and either including or excluding the decidual layer [5]. According to several studies, single-layer closure—especially with locked sutures—leads to significant thinning of the residual myometrium and a higher rate of niche formation [6,7]. One meta-analysis found that with single-layer closure, the mean residual myometrial thickness was 1.26 mm less (95% CI: 1.93–0.58), and the incidence of niche formation was 1.71 times higher (95% CI: 1.11–2.62) compared to double-layer closure [8]. Another study also confirmed that the residual myometrial thickness after double-layer closure was 9.95 ± 1.94 mm, whereas with single-layer closure it was 7.53 ± 2.54 mm ($P = 0.005$), indicating higher-quality healing in the double-layer group [9].

In addition to morphological changes in the scar, different closure techniques affect functional outcomes. Specifically, single-layer closure has been associated with a higher prevalence of dysmenorrhea, as demonstrated in the study by Chapman et al. [10]. The incidence of lower abdominal pain in women after single-layer closure was 1.23 times higher (95% CI: 1.01–1.48), potentially related to chronic inflammation at the site of an unstable scar or niche formation [11]. Moreover, myometrial thinning increases the risk of uterine rupture in subsequent pregnancies. A meta-analysis by Roberge et al. [12] found that the incidence of uterine rupture after single-layer closure was 1.91 times higher (95% CI: 0.63–5.74) than with double-layer closure. Yasmin et al. [13] also noted a greater frequency of scar dehiscence in repeat CS among women with single-layer closure.

Another key factor is whether the decidual layer is included or excluded during uterine closure. According to Hayakawa et al. [14], excluding the decidual layer leads to a higher rate of niches and poorer scar healing (RR 1.71; 95% CI: 1.11–2.62). Conversely, including the decidual layer improves vascularization and myometrial remodeling, thereby reducing the risk of niche formation and scar thinning [15].

Research findings suggest that the most advantageous closure method involves a two-layer, unlocked suture technique that includes the decidual layer. This approach ensures a thicker residual myometrium, lowers the incidence of niche formation, and improves the healing index (0.83 ± 0.10 vs. 0.67 ± 0.15 ; $P = 0.004$) [16]. Double-layer closure also decreases the amount of residual fluid in niches, reducing the risk of postmenstrual bleeding and improving menstrual function [17].

Despite the existing data, practice in uterine closure remains heterogeneous, and the choice of technique is often based on the surgeon's preferences rather than strict clinical guidelines [18]. This underscores the need for further research and the development of a

unified closure standard to minimize scar deformities, improve gynecological and reproductive outcomes, and enhance the safety of future pregnancies in women with uterine scars.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at maternity hospitals in the city of Samarkand and involved a retrospective review of medical records for 496 women who underwent cesarean section from 2019 to 2024. Based on the chosen method of uterine closure, the patients were divided into two groups: **Group 1 (n = 240)**—women who underwent modified uterine closure, and **Group 2 (n = 256)**—patients who received traditional suturing. Inclusion criteria were: age 18–42 years, absence of severe somatic and endocrine disorders, a history of one or two cesarean sections, and existing reproductive plans. Exclusion criteria included severe obstetric complications, congenital uterine anomalies, and uterine scarring following myomectomy.

Particular attention was paid to analyzing the frequency of reproductive losses (spontaneous miscarriages, missed miscarriages, elective terminations), the duration of the intergenetic interval, the condition of the uterine scar, the detection of gynecological diseases in the postoperative period, and contraceptive choices. Scar dehiscence was diagnosed by transvaginal ultrasound (TVUS) performed at 6, 12, and 24 months postoperatively. Residual myometrial thickness at the scar site was measured during physiological amenorrhea and in the early follicular phase of the menstrual cycle. Scar dehiscence was defined as a thickness less than 2.5 mm, or the presence of hypoechoic areas, deformations, or defects at the myometrial–endometrial junction.

Additional analyses evaluated the incidence of pelvic inflammatory diseases, menstrual disorders, chronic pelvic pain syndrome, and hyperplastic endometrial processes, including polyps and other pathologies associated with structural changes in the uterine cavity. Data on gynecological disease frequency were obtained from patients' outpatient records, reported complaints, and the results of colposcopic and hysteroscopic examinations.

The uterine suturing method was also assessed with regard to operative time, blood loss, and postoperative complications. In the modified closure group, modern suture materials were used to minimize tissue reactivity and were fully absorbed within 60–90 days. In the traditional group, a two-layer closure with separate interrupted sutures was employed.

All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 26.0. Quantitative variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation ($M \pm SD$). Between-group comparisons used the Student's t-test (for independent samples), the Mann–Whitney U-test, and the chi-square test for categorical data. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

1. Reproductive Losses

Analysis of the data showed a significant difference in the frequency of reproductive losses (spontaneous miscarriages, non-developing pregnancies, medical abortions) between the two groups. In the modified closure group, the rate of spontaneous miscarriages was 17.5%, whereas in the traditional closure group, it was 21.5%. The rate of non-developing pregnancies was 10.5% in the first group versus 18.0% in the second. These findings suggest that the modified closure technique exerts a positive influence on scar integrity and reduces the risk of reproductive losses.

Table 1.

Frequency of reproductive losses in the two groups

Outcome	Modified Closure (n, %)	Traditional Closure (n, %)	p-value
Spontaneous miscarriages	35 (17.5%)	47 (21.5%)	0.04
Non-developing pregnancy	21 (10.5%)	39 (18.0%)	0.01
Medical abortion	28 (14.0%)	53 (20.3%)	0.03
Two or more pregnancy losses	18 (9.2%)	41 (15.7%)	0.02

2. Duration of the Intergenic Interval

One crucial parameter for evaluating women’s reproductive health is the length of the intergenic interval. In the modified closure group, 82.5% of patients had a birth-to-birth interval of 18–24 months, whereas 67.2% did so in the traditional closure group. An interval of more than

24 months was more frequently observed among women in the traditional closure group (16.0% vs. 5.3% in the first group), which may indicate a longer period required for recovery of reproductive function. These findings suggest that the quality of scar formation after modified closure promotes faster restoration of fertility.

Table 2.

Duration of the intergenic interval in the two groups

Groups	<12 months (%)	12–18 months (%)	18–24 months (%)	>24 months (%)	Mean Interval (months)	p-value
Modified Closure	3.1	5.3	82.5	9.1	19.8	0.024
Traditional Closure	8.5	16.0	67.2	8.3	23.4	0.024

3. Condition of the Uterine Scar

Transvaginal ultrasound (TVUS) was used to objectively assess scar status. In the modified closure group, the mean residual myometrial thickness was 3.4 ± 0.5 mm, whereas in the traditional closure group, it

was 2.8 ± 0.6 mm. Scar dehiscence (a thickness <2.5 mm) was detected in 6.2% of patients in the first group and 14.5% of those in the second group, indicating more favorable anatomical outcomes with the modified technique.

Table 3.

Residual myometrial thickness in the two groups

Groups	Mean Myometrial Thickness (mm)	Scar Dehiscence (%)	Thickness <2.5 mm (%)	Thickness >3 mm (%)	p-value
Modified Closure	3.4	6.2	4.5	75.6	0.015
Traditional Closure	2.8	14.5	12.3	52.3	0.015

4. Frequency of Gynecological Disorders

An important aspect of postoperative follow-up is the incidence of gynecological disorders, including pelvic inflammatory diseases, endometrial hyperplasia, and chronic pelvic pain. In the traditional

closure group, inflammatory processes occurred in 28.5% of cases, compared with 17.5% in the modified closure group. These differences may be related to features of scar formation, changes in endometrial architecture, and myometrial vascularization.

Table 4.

Frequency of gynecological disorders in the two groups

Groups	Inflammatory Diseases (%)	Endometrial Hyperplasia (%)	Chronic Pelvic Pain (%)	Endometriosis (%)	Menstrual Cycle Disorders (%)	p-value
Modified Closure	17.5	10.5	12.0	8.3	15.0	0.022
Traditional Closure	28.5	18.0	22.5	14.7	21.5	0.022

5. Choice of Contraceptive Method

Analysis showed that the uterine closure technique influences women’s contraceptive preferences. In the modified closure group, 35.1% of women used barrier methods, 17.5% used combined oral contraceptives (COCs), and 15.8% chose intrauterine contraception. In

the traditional closure group, 13.3% used COCs, 16.8% used intrauterine contraception, and 30.1% used barrier methods. These findings indicate that women with a modified closure more frequently chose COCs, possibly due to reduced discomfort related to scar condition.

Table 5.

Contraceptive method selection in the two groups

Groups	Combined OCs (%)	Intrauterine Contraception (%)	Barrier Methods (%)	Withdrawal (%)	Contraception >1 year (%)	p-value
Modified Closure	17.5	15.8	35.1	31.6	45.3	0.029
Traditional Closure	13.3	16.8	30.1	39.8	38.7	0.029

Discussion of the Results

The findings convincingly demonstrate notable differences between various uterine closure methods following cesarean section. A lower rate of reproductive losses and higher scar integrity in patients undergoing the modified closure procedure confirm its advantages in terms of both preserving and restoring reproductive function. The significantly greater residual myometrial thickness in this group appears to reduce the risk of uterine rupture and improve the prognosis for subsequent pregnancies.

Moreover, the reduced incidence of inflammatory processes and hyperplastic disorders among women with the modified closure method indicates that this approach promotes more physiologically appropriate tissue healing and prevents adverse structural changes in the endometrium. Ultrasound data support the absence of significant scar deformities and a more uniform myometrial architecture, likely reflecting a favorable combination of factors—optimal tissue coaptation, minimal trauma, and sufficient vascularization at the scar site.

An interesting aspect of this study is the impact of the closure method on the length of the intergenetic interval. The data suggest that in the traditional closure group, the interval between pregnancies is often longer, which may be due not only to medical recommendations for prolonged recovery but also to a higher rate of complications necessitating additional treatment or rehabilitation. This factor is important for planning future pregnancies, particularly for women seeking to shorten the interval between deliveries.

The influence of uterine closure technique on contraceptive choice also merits attention. Patients who underwent the modified procedure more frequently opted for hormonal contraception (COCs), possibly owing to a more comfortable postoperative period, a lower risk of chronic pelvic pain, and a more favorable condition of the uterine scar. At the same time, women with traditional closure often chose barrier methods and were less likely to use COCs, potentially reflecting individual preferences and concerns about the safety of the scar under additional hormonal exposure.

These findings are consistent with numerous reports in the literature, suggesting that the use of more advanced (modified) suturing methods is associated with improved scar structure and a lower risk of defect formation. Nevertheless, it is important to bear in mind that the choice of closure technique may be influenced by clinical indications, the surgeon's experience, the resources available in the institution, and the patient's unique anatomical features.

Thus, employing modified uterine closure techniques after cesarean section appears to reduce the risk of scar dehiscence, enhance reproductive prospects, and decrease the incidence of gynecological disorders over the long term. Future research should focus on a more detailed analysis of the effects of different closure methods on myometrial function, as well as on evaluating long-term perinatal outcomes and patient quality of life. These findings underscore the need to refine surgical approaches to uterine closure and to develop evidence-based recommendations that will increase the safety and effectiveness of delivery via cesarean section.

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ЖУРНАЛ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ И УРО-НЕФРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 1

**JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH AND
URO-NEPHROLOGY RESEARCH**

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 1

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